

Lifestyle of Paliyar Tribes, Dindigul District, Tamilnadu, India

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ABSTRACT

Various tribes live in Kurinji, Mullai, Marutham, Neythal and Palai lands. Each tribe has many customs. Their way of life and culture still attracts everyone's attention. Paliyar tribe lives in the hills and forests of Kerala and Tamil Nadu. The Paliyar people have forever been the backbone of Tamil Nadu's history and culture. 46 types of tribes live in Tamil Nadu. Only 3.5% of the total population are tribals. Despite the small population, the language of the people living in each district is different. However, all their languages are closely related to Tamil. The people of Paliyar tribe are called Paniyars because they live on Palani Hill. Usually, Paliyar tribal people shift their living place because they do not have permanent houses and jobs. This led to complete trouble to the tribe. They are affected by both the individuals and the government officials. As the research continued about them many interesting facts came out. Paliyar tribes are more progressive than the mainstream society. The gender equality found in their society is unparalleled. This research paper clearly describes the history, culture, and lifestyle of Palliyar tribes. This research paper aims to focus on the growth, development, and mobility of tribals in the Dindigul district of Tamil Nadu and tries to convey geographical, historical, cultural and traditional approaches to others. This paper document their way of life, elucidate their habitats, and explain every facility provided by the government. It disseminates their rich socio-cultural heritage. It finds out how the rest of society sees them and how they practice a worthy life. Many factors influencing and determining different behavioural practices of Palliyar Tribal people such as economic status, social status, habits, and occupations. This paper predict ways and means to improve and enrich their cultural identity.

Key Words: Paliyar tribes, Geographical, Historical, Cultural, Palani Hill, Paniyars, Heritage

Introduction

India has a very large tribal population. A "tribe" is a social group having a distinct culture, having a common name, speaking a common language, observing uniform rules and working together for a common purpose, following traditions from ancestors. There are approximately 427 tribal communities in India. Many studies are done on such ethnic groups. Tribal communities meet their basic needs from the manufacture and sale of herbal medicines/drugs, which are derived from plants.

India has the largest number of indigenous peoples after Africa. According to the 2011 census, less than 9 per cent of the total population are tribal people living in India. Socially and economically backward, downtrodden and oppressed sections of tribals are found in East, Central and West regions of India. They practice cultivation, food gathering and fruit gathering for their livelihood. According to section 342 (1) of the Act, the President may, in consultation with the Governor, specify the locations of the tribal community or a subdivision of the tribal community to be treated as a Schedule Tribe. A tribal community can be included or excluded from a Schedule category by an Act of Parliament. Tribals constitute almost a quarter of India's total population. Their welfare and development are considered paramount in India's planning. In all developing countries, many special programs are implemented as the development and utilization of tribals. In the tribals' dignity, freedom of living and their self-respect and non-material needs are very closely observed. A multidimensional development dimension approach is very important to understand the Palliyar tribal people in Kodaikanal and Sirumalai. Paliar tribes depend on plant resources and have developed resource management systems based on habitat conservation.

The anthropological literature states that the tribals in India live in hilly, forested, hilly and forested terrains, rich in mineral, hydrological and forest resources. They live in isolated woodland habitats. Urban and peri-urban tribals are seen as distinct from the rest of the world in terms of social, economic and cultural life. Tribe is considered a term derived from the legacy of British colonial rule. And their life is unique to modern people. The life of the tribal people is different from the life of the people living on the coasts and islands. It is said that although the benefits of development have been given to improve the lives of the tribal people, it has not reached the people to the extent desired by the government. Social knowledge about tribal people is common to all. Article 275(1), supporting schemes for the development and welfare of Scheduled Tribes.

Paliyar Tribe

There are 37 tribal community in Tamilnadu. They are 1. Adiyar 2. Aranadan 3. Eravallan 4. Irular 5. Kadar 6. Kammara 7. Kanikaran 8. Kaniyan 9. Kattu Naickan 10. Kochuvelan 11. Konda Kapus 12. Konda Reddi 13. Koraga 14. Kota 15. Kudiya 16. Kurichchan 17. Kurumba 18. Kurumans 19. Maha Malasar 20. Malai Arayan 21. Malai Pandaram 22. Malai Vedan 23. Malakkuravan 24. Malasar 25. Malayali 26. Malaekandi 27. Mannan 28. Mudugar 29. Muthuvan 30. Palleyan 31. Palliyan 32. Palliyar 33. Paniyan 34. Sholagar 35. Toda 36. Urali 37. Narikoravan , Kuruvikkarar tribal communities.ⁱ They are having many best practicesⁱⁱ, excellent traditional knowledges, values. They are great asset to the society and forerunners to learn to live with nature.

According to the 1981 census, the total population of Palliyar, the indigenous inhabitants of Tamil Nadu, is 1613 (805 males & 808 females). The Palliyar tribe lives in the Western Ghats from the Palani Hills in the north to the Tirunelveli Hills in the south. They are an ancient tribe dating back to pre-Dravidian times. To this day it is widely believed that the Palliyar are natives of the Palani Hills. They are found in the Palani hills of Dindigul. Palliyan or Palliyar refers to those who live in places with red fields 'Palyar'. They called as Palliyar, Poliya, Pallayan. Palani people call them Malapaliyar. They are divided into two groups namely Vanapali and Deviya Pali. They are known as food gathering communities of Tamil Nadu. The word 'Palliyar' is derived from the word 'Palanian' which means man from Palani in Tamil. They speak Tamil and use the Tamil alphabet. Tribals have built grass huts with only one room to live in. There are doors on both sides of the hut. The Palliyar tribe is completely illiterate. Only a few can count to ten. Since the Palliyar lives in remote areas of the forest, they are not very interested in enrolling tribal children in remote areas formal schools. In Palliyar tribal society, there are no elected or appointed leaders. An elder person takes the lead if a decision is taken to protect the welfare of the people. As far as health care practices are concerned, no change can be seen among them even today.ⁱⁱⁱ

Tribal Society

The Paliyas generally lived in large stone caves in the mountains. When there were no stone caves, they lived in the earth cave. Living in groups is the most common activity found in Paliyar society. Both men and women participate in the group. Women's participation in the group to make important decisions is the best activity found among the multiracial population. Each group has a leader who makes key decisions. That the chief remains an unmarried youth is the best practice

among the Paliyas people. Problems are discussed before the chairman of the committee and solutions are found. Problems cannot be taken beyond them. Even if there are any problems between a man and a woman, it is the duty of this committee to resolve them by talking to the families of both of them. It is a great activity to resolve any problem within the groups among people of different races.^{iv}

Palliyar tribesmen go to fieldwork early in the morning. A few Palliyar tribesmen bathe in the morning. Mostly rice, ragi, and small millets are taken as food. The dried parts of the plants are used by the Palliyar tribesmen as herbal medicine for all ailments. Palliyar society did not wear clothes in the early period. They started wearing clothes only in the twentieth century. Men wore dhoti around their waists instead of wearing proper clothes. Paliyar women wore men's clothes. Due to the later modernization, the Paliyar women changed their lifestyle by wearing sari and other modern clothes and started settling in the hills to expose themselves to the outside world. Eating cassava and hunting animals is the custom of Palliyar. Paliyars are hunters and food gatherers. Only men go hunting to protect their families, is a particular activity found among people of Paliyar society. It is remarkable that all girls belonging to this community are brought up together by the women of Paliyar society.^v

The Paliyars channeled the forest deities and nature. Their specialty is to talk to animals when they see them while walking in the forest. Apart from that, it is customary for the animals to nod and move away after listening to their speech. When the animals remain silent, the people of the community move away. Paliyars loved nature a lot. They depended on forests for their livelihood and food. They used the forest only for their needs. They do not do anything more than necessary. They always took care not to harm the forest. Conservation of water resources was their main activity. Cutting down dead trees and planting more trees is a special feature of the Paliyar community. Never used pills when sick. Nature is their medicine.^{viii} Worshiping God: The tribal people pray to Karuppan, the forest deity in the forest. In early times the pilgrims were allowed to perform puja, but today this right has been taken away. However, the Paliyar community has a custom of going to the forest and performing puja with family members. Kodaikanal Paliyars say that Valli, the wife of Lord Subramanian, was a Paliyar woman, who served as a night watchman in the foothills. They worship stones and goddess idols (Pallichiamman). Palliyar tribal community has beliefs in superstitious activities.

Kothali was the head of the village. His beautiful girl was Palichi. The father usually went into the forest to collect honey, mustard gooseberry, dig tubers, etc., and started doing work in early

morning. At the same time, it was the mother's job to bring honey, mustard seeds, gooseberry tubers down from the mountain and sell them to buy the things she needed. All the houses were made of bamboo. The top was covered with fennel. Animals like leopards, tigers, lions, and elephants were seen there. So no one comes out of the house. They are always indoors. One day the parents went out of the house. Then Palichi was alone. When a young man named Manikkodi came to the forest to buy bamboo rice, his throat became dry due to thirst. Everywhere in the forest was dry without water. Manikodi came to Balichu's house in search of water. Manikodi gave him water. A great bond was formed between the two. After Manikodi left, Palichi gave up his life thinking of him. The villagers started worshiping their ancestral deity Palichi. Palichiamman has been worshiped since then till today. Palichiamman is not given an image. People of Paliyar race worship only stone as an image.^{viii}

Celebration of Festivals: During all festivals, they buy and eat rice at a reasonable price from the ration shop. Paliyar. Palliyar celebrates various festivals such as Festival of new lentil (Kandikotha), the festival of new sprouting (a kudu kotha), the festival of new fruit growing (Kondamkotha), the festival of tiger (Pulipanduka), the festival of the goddess, the festival of village god, bethakam for each millet harvest, the festival of stars and festival of the new harvest of mangoes.^{ix} **Celebrations And Adornments:** Paliyar men and women do not give importance to ornaments. They do not wear ornaments even during festivals. The more sophisticated women, however, wore studs made of brass, studded with beads and cheap imitation stones. Although the Paliyar tribes are economically and socially backward, and they do not know to lead a hidden life. **Eating Habits:** They are vegetarians but do not eat beef and pork. Their staple food grains are rice and ragi. They consume all types of pulses and use groundnut oil and palm oil for cooking. They consume tubers, vegetables, fruits and milk, and milk products, and drink black tea and black coffee. Both men and women of this community drink alcohol regularly. They smoke beedi, cigarettes and eat betel nut. They give goods, roots, fruits, and honey from the forest with the Palani low hill habited people and receive betel nut, chillies, rice, and nuts in return. **Burial Practices:** Dead bodies are not cremated. They used to bury the bodies of dead near their residential areas in the west.

Tribal Economy

They know the nooks and corners of the deep forests. Hunting was the main occupation. They used weapons like bows and arrows for hunting. They used to hunt deer and rabbits with the help of dogs. In early times they were nomadic. They had knowledge about medicinal plants and

herbs. They can identify many medicinal plants. They prepare medicines and use them to treat common ailments like colds, coughs and headaches, snake bites, venomous insect bites, and digestive disorders. Honey Collection: Palliyar tribes collect honey from trees and rock caves. They use honey as a barter for manufactured goods such as tools, pots, clothes, and ornaments. Fishing: One of the main industries is fishing. They catch crabs from mountain rivers and streams. Agriculture: The Palliyar tribe cultivates ragi, millet, paddy, coffee, banana, etc. in the surrounding areas and leases land from some other castes to grow coffee, ginger, potato, etc. They collect food and other things in the forest. They work as laborers on farms in the valleys. The people who migrated from the forests to the plains took up agriculture as their occupation. They collect wild plants from forests and use them medicinally. In fact, they live in poverty. People nearby exploit them.^x Paliyars in Kadugu Thadi: Paliyars in Kadugu Thadi, near the better known Thandikudi, in the Kodaikanal taluk of Tamil Nadu are different from Paliyars from Palani. Earlier tribes were hunter-gatherers and lived in caves in the mountains. Now, they work as daily wage laborers, engage in beekeeping, cultivate food, and sell forest products. Soil, powdered stones and coal were used in the earlier to brush the teeth. Paliyar tribes are used Crushed and powdered Mustard seeds (*Brassica campestris*), Chaff-Flower (*Achyranthes aspera*), Clove (*Syzygium aromaticum*), for toothaches.^{xi}

Constitutional Welfare Measures

Tribes contribute to the ethnic diversity and rich cultural of India and play a major role in biodiversity conservation, forests protection. 8.6% of India's Population, as per Census 2011, constitutes Schedule Tribes. The socio-economic development of the tribes ensures by the Constitution of India. Article 46 of the Constitution empowers the State to protect Tribes from social injustice and all forms of exploitation to promote education and economic. Article 15(4) of the Constitution provides reservation in the educational institution and Articles 16(4), 16(4A) and 16(4B) of the Constitution provides reservation in posts and services. Parliament has enacted the Bonded Labour System (Abolition) Act, 1976 based on the Article 23 of the Constitution which protects Scheduled Tribes from traffic in human beings and beggars and forced labour. Article 24 protects Scheduled Tribes from 14 years below children employment in hazardous factory or mine. The Constitution provides reservation of seats for Scheduled Tribes in Panchayats (Article 243D), House of the People (Article 330), Legislative Assemblies of the States (Article 332), Lok Sabha and the State Vidhan Sabhas (Article 334).

Article 275: Every year Government of India provides grants-in-aid from the Consolidated Fund of India (Article 275(1) of the Constitution of India) to promote Infrastructure development schemes such as protected drinking water, road connectivity, electricity and housing for the welfare of Scheduled Tribes. Based on Infrastructure development schemes, Eklavya Model Residential School (EMRS) for Tribal students functioning at Vellimalai in Villupuram, Salem, Nilgiris, Tiruvannamalai, Vellore, Namakkal and Kanchipuram District but not reached in Dindigal District in Tamil Nadu.

Scheduled Tribes and Other Traditional Forest Dwellers (Recognition of Forest Rights) Act, 2006, issues Pattas to the Tribals who are residing in the forest before 13.12.2005 and provides funds from Consolidated fund. The traditional forest dwellers for 3 generations i.e., for 75 years prior to 13.12.2005 receives the forest rights from the State Government. Title deeds have been distributed to the claimants. In order to implement this Act, the State Government have constituted State Level Monitoring Committee headed by the Chief Secretary, District Level Committee headed by the District Collector and Sub-Divisional Level Committee – headed by the Revenue Divisional Officer. Under Article 275(1) the Ministry of Tribal Affairs, set aside 10% of the allocation to States as incentive for innovative schemes for the promotion of development programmes such as medical units' setup, children's health awareness camps, agricultural latest technology activities, setting up of correct barter rates depicting sign boards and better communication system. Integrated Tribal Development Programme (ITDP) is implemented at Yercaud Pachamalai, Aranuthumalai & Kalrayan Hills in Salem District, at Kolli Hills in Namakkal District, at Kalrayan Hills in Villupuram District, at Jawadhu Hills in Tiruvannamalai District, at Pachamalai in Tiruchirappalli District, at Sitheri Hills in Dharmapuri District, at Jawadhu & Yelagiri Hills in Vellore District but not in Dindigal District in Tamil Nadu.

To raise the economic and social status of tribal people, income generating programmes are provided under Special Central Assistance to Tribal Sub Plan (SCA to TSP). Out of total SC-A allotment, 60% for economic development, 30% for infrastructure development and 10% for imparting Skill Development Training to the ST Youths. The State Government is receiving, incentive amount since 2004-2005 from Central Government to implement schemes for employment and income generating activities for the benefit of the tribals. But Palliyar tribes still struggling for the development. An amount of Rs.5.18 crore has been allocated under Comprehensive Tribal Development Programme (CTDP) through TAHDCO for the implementation of infrastructure works. Toilet, Bathrooms, Borewells with motors, drinking water,

Electricity construction in 128 Government Tribal Residential Schools located at Villupuram, Dharmapuri, Namakkal, Salem, Vellore, Tiruchirappalli, Thiruvannamalai, Coimbatore, The Nilgiris, Tirunelveli, Erode, Tiruppur Districts are under progress. Comprehensive Tribal Development Programme (CTDP) is still not extended to Tribals in Dindigul District.

Pre-Matric Scholarship Scheme is provided for students studying in IX & X in recognized institutions. It is launched by Government of India for Scheduled Tribe. Total expenditure bears by the Government of India. For Higher Secondary, Arts, Science, Commerce and Professional Courses studying students, both residential and Non-residential scholarships are awarded. In Tamilnadu many tribes receive facilities like traditional houses construction, milch animals' distribution, drinking water provision, street lights, Primary Health Centres, Fishing Nets, Two Wheelers, Beehive boxes, Brick kiln, Bore-wells, check dam for irrigation and, Road facilities. The EMR School started in June 2018 at Pattipulam in Kancheepuram District. For the conveyance of people and students from the hill to plain area and vice versa, two Eicher Cab in the Nilgiris District started. Such type of EMR School and Eicher Cab are not started for Palliyar tribes in Dindigul District.

Conclusion

The nation accommodates diverse people in multi cultures and linguistics. The tribe is categorized as a scheduled tribe with natural rights. The state recognizes the tribes and tribal areas on the basis of considering their cultures and customs. Social relations often begin with a certain amount of sizing up based on ethnic group. The family, village community, and caste system are great contrasts. Tribal people should be allowed to develop on the lines of their own genius and nothing should be imposed upon them; Tribal rights in land and forest should be respected; Induction of too many outsiders into tribal areas should be avoided. There should be no over-administration of tribal areas and as far as possible work should be done through their own social and cultural institutions. The results should be judged not by the amount of money spent but by the quality of human character that is evolved. Tribes differ from vast differences in a socioeconomic status where millions of people live amidst roaring vehicles, crowds, jammed buildings, busy commercial establishments, and loudspeakers blaring movie tunes while breathing the poisons of industrial and automotive pollution.

Palliyar tribes living in the Dindigul District are engaged in the activity of hunting gathering, honey collecting, and medical herbs. They also consume all kinds of pulse and use groundnut, and palm as cooking oil and eat vegetables, fruits, milk, and milk products, and drink

black tea and black coffee. The present society is predominantly under elite command, the customs, style of life, and culture. The tribes, on the other hand, are people with special attachments to land, kinship ties, a unique culture, certain religious beliefs, particular activities, or material possessions that differentiated and separated them from the mainstream. The tribes have less political power and less access to resources, technology, and other forms of power. Though technology is distant to the tribal people, there are bound by value systems and are adopted in proportion to the natural stream. Their cultural practices are honored. Though many acts are implemented by the Central government, State government, and local government, but still the efforts of the government did not reach the tribes. The research will bring out new insights into the good practices prevailing among the Palliyar tribes and actions need to take to protect the Tribes. Though Palliar community not receiving many benefits, Palliar tribes cultivate their lands using pre-agricultural technology. Palliar tribes are economically backward. Palliar tribes' level of literacy is very low. It is need of the hour to provide agricultural development and cattle development to generate income and to create necessary infrastructure for their sustenance and their overall development.

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